
THE VALIDITY OF SCHMIDT-APPLEMAN CRITERION IN MODERN TURBOFAN ENGINES: A NUMERICAL STUDY

✉ **Manas Payyappalli, Gijs Frehe, Feijia Yin, Arvind Gangoli Rao**

Faculty of Aerospace Engineering
TU Delft

2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands

m.payyappalli@tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

Contrails are line-shaped clouds formed behind aircraft under specific atmospheric conditions. They have significant implications in aviation-induced climate effects due to their role in altering atmospheric radiative forcing. A simple thermodynamic theory that is still widely used is the Schmidt-Appleman (SA) criterion which gives a temperature threshold to predict the formation of contrails. This paper uses a macrophysical approach utilising thermodynamic relations for phase change to predict contrail formation from aircraft engine exhausts and compares with the Schmidt-Appleman criterion. RANS simulations are carried out using a commercial CFD solver to simulate turbofan engine exhausts under various conditions. The potential phase change regions downstream of the engine exhaust are modeled using Gibbs Free Energy, a derived thermodynamic parameter, that often is used in explaining cloud formation. The study compares how bypass ratio influences contrail formation regions and compares the results with that obtained using the Schmidt-Appleman criterion.

Keywords non-CO₂ emissions · contrails formation · turbofan engine · climate change

1 Introduction

With the increasing demand for air travel, aviation climate impact has become a significant concern. Although aircraft technology has been looking at improving the carbon footprint of aviation, non-CO₂ emissions also have a significant impact on climate change. The vast majority of non-CO₂ emissions are condensation trails, also known as contrails. In fact, contrails are reported to have a global warming potential of about 35-60% [1, 2] of the total aviation climate impact. However, these estimates are based on modeling approaches that involve large uncertainties in their predictions. Traditionally, turbofan engine architectures have been advancing in the direction of increasing fuel efficiency. While increasing fuel efficiency is important, reducing contrails is also equally important, especially in the context of modern turbofans that could potentially use new fuels such as sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) or hydrogen. Several works have discussed contrails and their potential radiative forcing in detail [2–6] and resonates on the fact that understanding the formation and evolution of contrails is important to obtain a good prediction of radiative forcing of contrails. Hence, a more detailed understanding of the formation and evolution of contrails is necessary to estimate its global warming potential. Contrails typically form when hot and humid exhaust gases of an engine mixes with the cold ambient air [7]. Therefore, the formation of contrails is a multi-physics problem which lies at the intersection of thermodynamics, fluid mechanics, and physical chemistry and is hugely dependent on engine conditions and atmospheric variables.

The Schmidt-Appleman (SA) criterion is foundational in understanding contrail formation and determines the thermodynamic conditions under which contrails form. Schmidt [8] proposed a theoretical framework relating aircraft exhaust and atmospheric conditions which was further refined by Appleman [9], allowing prediction of contrail formation based on engine exhaust conditions and ambient temperature and pressure. This proves research on contrails started decades ago, although the focus then was primarily due to military interests. A detailed explanation to the SA criterion is given in Section 2. The climate concerns that we are experiencing today have led to a more focused approach on quantifying the radiative forcing, the aviation sector also diligently trying to reduce its climate impacts. It is worth noting that, a few

decades ago, the Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC) in 1999, brought out a comprehensive assessment of the impact of aviation on climate change. From then on, contrails, along with other anthropogenic emissions from aviation, has gained renewed attention.

In a couple of his technical articles, Schumann [10, 11] investigated the conditions of formation of contrails and revisits the SA criterion. The article derives the conditions for contrail formation by including the effects of conversion of the exhaust heat into kinetic energy and finds that the threshold temperatures increase in such a case. The paper states the threshold temperature may depend on turbulent mixing in the near field especially for modern turbofan engines. The paper also verifies the applicability of the SA criterion in a broad sense, however, also mentions that detailed understanding is required to comprehend how different engine and atmospheric parameters affect contrail formation and the radiative forcing by aviation.

Paoli et al [12] simulated the formation and immediate evolution of contrail in the near field using Large Eddy Simulations (LES) in a coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian framework to model the flow-field and the microphysical nature of ice formation. The work emphasises the importance of the aircraft wake vortex, jet, and entrainment dynamics in contrail formation. Another study using LES was carried out by Shirgaonkar et al. [13] and had the objective of understanding the sensitivity of contrails to atmospheric conditions. This study also used a coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian framework and concluded that one dominant feature affecting contrail formation in the early phase is the turbulent mixing of the jet and the free atmosphere. It is worth noting that in a turbofan in reality, the mixing happens between the core and bypass jets and the freestream atmosphere, leading to a rather complex mixing phenomenon influencing contrail formation. The article also gives insight into how exhaust temperature affects growth rates of contrails.

A similar study but using a theoretical approach was put forward by Kärcher et al. [2], where the microphysical and optical properties of contrail particles in the near field of engine exhaust were modeled based on cloud theory and thermodynamics of exhaust jets. The model, being microphysical in nature, identifies the dependence of ice particle numbers and size of the particles on the emission indices of soot.

Cantin et al. [14] utilised a coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian model to implement an ice-microphysical module in a Eulerian framework that solves the flow physics. The model uses a turbofan with a bypass ratio of 5.3 and conditions that are representative of flight cruising. The model is reported to show good agreement of plume dilution and ice-particle properties. Ice particles were found to grow and thicken that correlated with the presence of external shear layer. The work infers that the core axis of the plume was saturated at a downstream distance of about 55 times the diameter of the bypass duct. The study also carries out an interesting optical-depth analysis that shows the contrail was visible around 26 m downstream from the engine exit.

Although previous studies have given good insight on contrail formation through modeling and simulations, the influence of mixing and the near-field dynamics are still topics that greatly depend on the engine architecture and atmospheric conditions. In fact, several works discussed above have highlighted the importance of the near-field mixing. Therefore, in a realistic scenario, understanding the influence of the bypass ratios in modern turbofan engines and their mixing phenomenon are of great importance to understand how contrails form. In this context, we plan to extend the current understanding of contrails in a direction to explore the near-field contrail formation within the context of modern turbofan engines. We look in the near-field of the aircraft to understand the validity of the SA criterion and compare with the observations that we obtain for different turbofan engines from a macrophysical perspective. The flowfields and thermodynamic conditions in the near field of three modern turbofan engines are compared using computational fluid dynamics (CFD). The subsequent sections explain the adopted methodology and the observations from simulations. Towards the end of this article, we propose suggestions for future studies and outline the directions in which we plan to carry this work forward.

2 Methodology

In order to check the influence of the bypass ratio and other operating conditions of turbofans, three engine models have been investigated that operate under nearly similar cruise conditions. CFM56-3, CFM LEAP-1A35, and an ultra-bypass ratio engine (named as UHBR-2050 engine) with a bypass ratio higher than the former two engines are analysed. The bypass ratios of all three engines are given in Table 1. The geometries of CFM56-3 and LEAP-1A35 are obtained from the works of Cantin et al. [14, 15] and the UHBR-2050 is designed through a Python-based engine cycle model [16]. All engines are assumed to cruise at a height of approximately 35000 ft where the ambient temperature is 219 K. The mass fraction of water vapor in the ambient was calculated as 6.22×10^{-5} for the ice-supersaturated conditions. The mass fractions of water vapor in the core inlet is calculated as 0.020 for the CFM56-3 and LEAP-1A35 engines and 0.018 for the UHBR-2050 engine.

Engine	BPR
CFM56-3	6
CFM LEAP-1A35	11
UHBPR-2050	16

Table 1: Different engines and their bypass ratios

The exhausts from these engines are investigated using CFD simulations which is set up as a 2D-axisymmetric problem in the commercial solver ANSYS Fluent 2023 R2 that solves the steady Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes equations (RANS) in a finite volume framework. In addition, the solver is also implemented with species transport models to consider the distribution of water vapor in the exhaust plume and ambient.

The domain is set up with a dimension of $200m \times 200m$ which according to the scope of this paper serves the purpose of looking at the near-field region of contrail formation. The domain has fully structured mesh generated with the help of the inbuilt meshing software in Fluent. A density-based implicit solver is used to solve the collection of governing fluid dynamics equations. The core and bypass inlets are initialised with mass flow boundary conditions, while the ambient inlet is initialised with a velocity boundary condition. The outlet of the domain is imposed by the pressure conditions, and the ambient is imposed with pressure far-field boundary condition. The surfaces are defined as no-slip walls and the axis of the domain has an axisymmetric boundary condition. The boundary conditions for the inlets of the engine are calculated using isentropic calculations and the engine performance model [16], which allowed to carry out a sensitivity assessment of the boundary conditions. The calculations are compared and validated with the conditions of CFM56-3 case stated in Cantin et al. [14]. However, for the simulations, the boundary conditions for all engines are chosen based on the outputs of the engine performance model in order to maintain consistency between the different cases investigated.

A systematic grid independence study is carried out to ensure that the mesh is able to capture the flow physics and this exercise concluded that around 0.6 million cells are necessary to obtain the flowfield. In addition, a turbulence model verification and a study to validate the solver was carried out. The description of the geometry of the engines and a sample mesh is given in Figure 1. The respective dimensions of the engines are presented in Table 2.

Figure 1: Schematic of the geometry and a sample mesh

Dimension	CFM56-3	LEAP-1A35	UHBPR-2050
Nozzle radius, R_N	0.95	1.11	1.20
Bypass outer radius, $R_{b,outer}$	0.79	1.04	1.15
Bypass inner radius, $R_{b,inner}$	0.53	0.62	0.51
Core outer radius, $R_{c,outer}$	0.32	0.47	0.33
Core inner radius, $R_{c,inner}$	0.22	0.31	0.08
Nozzle length, L_N	1.74	1.79	2.66
Bypass plug length, $L_{b,plug}$	2.62	2.80	3.51
Core plug length, $L_{c,plug}$	3.01	3.60	3.75

Table 2: Geometric description of the engines

Since data corresponding to actual engine conditions are not available in public domain, a coaxial subsonic turbulent jet [17] and a near-sonic jet [18]. After validating against experimental data $\kappa - \omega - SST$ model was selected as the turbulence model for the engine simulations. In view of the limited space available in the article, details of validation are not included in the paper.

2.1 Schmidt-Appleman (SA) criterion

The SA criterion integrates the conservation of energy in jet exhaust with ambient humidity conditions. According to SA criterion, contrail formation occurs when the saturation vapor pressure over water in the exhaust plume falls below that in the surrounding atmosphere. This thermodynamic approach is based on the assumption that contrails form when the plume with water vapor surpasses water-saturation conditions, supporting the formation and growth of water droplets. The SA criterion primarily allows to draw a line (called the mixing line) connecting the exhaust and ambient conditions. The slope of the mixing line $G(Pa/K)$ can then be calculated as follows;

$$G = \frac{p_e^{H_2O} - p_\infty^{H_2O}}{T_e - T_\infty} \quad (1)$$

where T_e and $p_e^{H_2O}$ are the temperature and pressure at the exhaust of the engine and T_∞ and $p_\infty^{H_2O}$ are the temperature and pressure in the ambient. Schumann [10] made an approximation of the mixing line slope and expressed it in the parameters associated with the engine.

$$G = p_\infty c_p \frac{M_{air}}{M_{H_2O}} \frac{EI_{H_2O}}{(1 - \eta)Q} \quad (2)$$

Where p_∞ is the ambient air pressure, c_p is the specific heat capacity of air, M_{air} and M_{H_2O} are the molar masses of air and water, respectively, EI_{H_2O} is the emissions index of water vapor, η is the overall propulsive efficiency, and Q is the specific heat capacity of the fuel used.

2.2 Gibbs free energy

Cloud formation is often explained with the help of Gibbs free energy. Gibbs free energy, defined in Equation 3 is obtained by carrying out a Legendre transformation to a standard thermodynamic variable, the enthalpy. Thus, the Gibbs free energy is obtained by subtracting the product of temperature, T and entropy, s from the enthalpy, H.

Gibbs free energy (GFE) is defined as the maximum amount of work performed at constant pressure and temperature in a closed system. Every system or particle has a certain amount of GFE depending on its state. Mathematically, GFE can be quantified as follows;

$$G = H - TS \quad (3)$$

In other words,

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (4)$$

This equation holds valid for a closed system, and in the present article, it is assumed that the cells of the fluid domain are closed systems. For contrail formation, water vapor in the plume should freeze and this means the phenomenon will be associated with a phase change from water vapor to solid. The phase change of a thermodynamic state can be considered to occur if the change in GFE is negative. Although, a microphysical phase change is not the scope of the

paper, the idea is to carry out a macrophysical thermodynamic state analysis of the fluid domain to assess the potential regions of phase change. For a detailed understanding of thermodynamics of cloud formation, readers are suggested to look through the book "An Introduction to Clouds" [19].

The change in GFE can also be written as

$$\Delta G = \Delta G^\circ - \Delta G_p \quad (5)$$

Here, ΔG° corresponds to the reference state ($T = 298.15K$, $P = 1 \cdot 10^5 Pa$) and ΔG_p corresponds to the change due to saturation pressure. ΔG° and ΔG_p can be expressed as

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta G_p = RT * \ln\left(\frac{p_{H_2O}}{p_{si,H_2O}}\right) \quad (7)$$

where, the partial pressure of water vapor, p_{H_2O} is calculated using the Dalton's Law and the saturation pressure over ice, $p_{si}^{H_2O}$ is calculated using the Sonntag formula [20].

Figure 2: GFE distribution of different engine cases in the entire simulation domain

3 Results & Discussion

We compare three configurations - CFM56-3, CFM LEAP-1A35, and the UHBR-2050 engine. For a standard cruise operating condition of the three engines, the GFE distribution is shown in Figure 2. For all engine cases, it is interesting to note that GFE starts to become negative in the shear layer and these are seen as thin lines that stretch gradually into more area of the plume. This means the likelihood of phase change is higher in the shear layers in the very near field of the engine. For all three engine cases, the distribution of GFE in the simulation domain is relatively similar. The GFE starts to become negative a few metres downstream of the engines particularly within the region of the core jet. This is

obvious because the core of the engine has high water vapor content. However, the centreline of the core of the jet also has high temperature and therefore, GFE is not negative in the centerline in the vicinity of the engine.

A closer observation of the contours shows that the onset of negative GFE and its evolution are different in all the three cases. On a qualitative note, high negative GFE (the relatively white regions in Figure 3) is observed to initiate in regions closer to the engine exhaust in the case of CFM56-3 as compared to the other two cases. The negative GFE regions also spread to wider radii downstream for the CFM56-3 engine as compared to the other two engines. Technically, there are competing characteristics of the flow and the ambient that contribute to the actual formation of contrails. For example, the entrainment of water vapor from the ambient to the plume due to turbulent mixing is a primary factor that will affect contrail formation. In addition, the bypass ratios are different for all the three engines and therefore, the strength of the shear layers will be different. This will significantly affect the local temperature and pressure distributions and result in difference in contrail forming regions.

Figure 3: GFE distribution of different engine cases in the very near-field (0 m to 80 m)

To get an idea of the mixing process, radial distribution of axial velocity, static temperature, and turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) are shown in Figures 4 - 6. The plots show the profiles of the flow variables from the axis to a location of 2 m in the radial direction. The axial velocity at the centerline is highest for CFM56 as compared to other two engines. The shear layer is found to dissipate with the core and bypass flow showing a smooth transition of velocity for the CFM56, while this also comes with a large gradient between the freestream and the centerline velocity. Therefore, strong mixing is likely to take place downstream of $x = 10$ m to smoothen the velocity profiles. This is evident at $x = 40$ m, where the velocity profiles relatively have less gradient. From the velocity profiles, it is clear that significant mixing happens in the very near-field of the engine and this differs between the engines. In any case, it is observed that by the time the jets reach $x = 40$ m and $x = 70$ m, the velocity gradients between the centerline and the freestream are reduced and most of the mixing happens in the near-field.

The temperature distribution at $x = 10$ m shows a similar trend between the engines and shows a smooth transition to the core centerline temperature from the freestream. However, it is observed that the centerline temperature is high for LEAP-1A35 at $x = 40$ m and is approximately 350 K and it decays to around 300 K at $x = 80$ m. This

means LEAP1A-35 is less prone to contrail formation in the centerline in the vicinity of the engine exhaust since the temperature is high and water vapor in the centerline will require more energy to undergo phase change.

The TKE of the three engines show that LEAP-1A35 and the CFM56-3 has the highest kinetic energy in the very near field which therefore enhances the mixing process. The UHBR engine has relatively low TKE as compared to other engine cases. In general, the mixing continues to occur from the engine exhaust to downstream and therefore, the role mixing plays in stabilising the flow conditions is significant. More clarity is needed on how exactly each flow variable contribute to the phase change and a more detailed analysis on the flow variables is required to correctly predict the conditions influencing phase change.

Figure 4: Radial distribution of axial velocity at different downstream locations (a) 10 m (b) 40 m (c) 70 m

Figure 5: Radial distribution of static temperature at different downstream locations (a) 10 m (b) 40 m (c) 70 m

Figure 6: Radial distribution of turbulent kinetic energy at different downstream locations (a) 10 m (b) 40 m (c) 70 m

The different engine types are compared to quantify the effect of bypass ratio on contrail formation. Mixing lines are plotted between the engine exhaust and the domain exit conditions and are shown in Figure 7. It should be noted that the EI is relatively different for the three engines. UHBR-2050 has a higher temperature at the end of the domain due to a longer potential core, LEAP-1A35 has the steepest mixing line showing the most likelihood of contrail formation. It should be noted that the temperature in the plume at the exit of the domain does not reach ambient conditions for all three cases and therefore, more analysis is required with a larger length of domain to understand the formation and persistence of contrails.

Figure 7: Schmidt-Appleman condition, with mixing lines for all the engines.

A comparison has been made between the regions in the fluid domain where the SA criterion is met and the regions where the GFE predicts phase change potential and this is shown in 8, with the SA criterion contour colored in red. The SA criterion seems to be more stringent and shows potential contrail regions mainly in the shear layer towards the edge of the negative GFE contours. SA will therefore give a more critical prediction on if contrails will form or not. However, since there is no dimensionality involved in the expression of SA criterion, it also lacks the prediction of the size and distribution of the phase change potential. In this context, GFE might be a useful predictive tool that could give insights into the expected size of contrail distribution.

4 Conclusion

The paper investigates contrail formation potential for modern turbofan engines through numerical simulations using thermodynamic parameters. Engines with different bypass ratios are investigated and it is seen that with increasing bypass ratio the area of potential contrail formation decreases. This primarily shows that contrail formation is likely to be delayed for high bypass ratio engines. The onset of contrail strongly depends on the decay of temperature from the exhaust and obviously, a slower temperature dissipation is found to delay the onset of contrail formation. This is also associated with the dynamics of axial velocity and TKE distribution downstream in the plume.

The GFE is able to predict the potential contrail forming areas while the SA criterion appears to underpredict them. However, we need more in situ validation of this method to confirm the formation regions and persistence of contrails. The GFE also predicts that contrail formation could potentially initiate in the shear layers between the core and bypass jets. Broadly, the SA criterion is more stringent, however, SA criterion is still useful as it allows an easy prediction of formation and persistence of contrails based on simple thermodynamic conditions. The assumption of SA criterion such as isobaric and instantaneous mixing is not valid in reality especially for modern turbofan engines that have strong shocks and mixing.

Figure 8: SA criterion (colored in red) overlapped on the GFE contour. Atmospheric conditions are $T = 219K$, $RH = 60\%$.

The authors plan to take this work forward by incorporating high fidelity simulations to understand the mixing process in the near-field and to improve the understanding of contrail formation in realistic turbofan engines. Future work will also be supported with microphysics modules that will allow to model ice particle formation in the nearfield.

5 Acknowledgements

This project has received co-funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101096275 and from the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee number 10068673.

References

- [1] David S Lee, David W Fahey, Piers M Forster, Peter J Newton, Ron CN Wit, Ling L Lim, Bethan Owen, and Robert Sausen. Aviation and global climate change in the 21st century. *Atmospheric environment*, 43(22-23):3520–3537, 2009.
- [2] Bernd Kärcher. Formation and radiative forcing of contrail cirrus. *Nature communications*, 9(1):1824, 2018.
- [3] Patrick Minnis, Ulrich Schumann, David R Doelling, Klaus M Gierens, and David W Fahey. Global distribution of contrail radiative forcing. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 26(13):1853–1856, 1999.
- [4] Ulrich Schumann. Formation, properties and climatic effects of contrails. *Comptes Rendus Physique*, 6(4-5):549–565, 2005.

- [5] Ulrike Burkhardt and Bernd Kärcher. Global radiative forcing from contrail cirrus. *Nature climate change*, 1(1):54–58, 2011.
- [6] Dharmendra Kumar Singh, Swarnali Sanyal, and Donald J Wuebbles. Understanding the role of contrails and contrail cirrus in climate change: a global perspective. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 24(16):9219–9262, 2024.
- [7] Roberto Paoli and Karim Shariff. Contrail modeling and simulation. *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, 48(1):393–427, 2016.
- [8] Ernst Schmidt. Die entstehung von eisnebel aus den auspuffgasen von flugmotoren. *Schriften der Deutschen Akademie der Luftfahrtforschung, Verlag R. Oldenbourg, München, Heft 44*, 5(44):1–15, 1941.
- [9] Herbert Appleman. The formation of exhaust condensation trails by jet aircraft. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 34(1):14–20, 1953.
- [10] Ulrich Schumann. On conditions for contrail formation from aircraft exhausts. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, 5:4–23, 1996.
- [11] Ulrich Schumann. Influence of propulsion efficiency on contrail formation. *Aerospace science and technology*, 4(6):391–401, 2000.
- [12] Roberto Paoli, Jerome Helie, and Thierry Poinot. Contrail formation in aircraft wakes. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 502:361–373, 2004.
- [13] Anup Shirgaonkar and Sanjiva Lele. Large eddy simulation of early stage contrails: Effect of atmospheric properties. In *44th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit*, page 1414, 2006.
- [14] Sébastien Cantin, Mohamed Chouak, François Morency, and François Garnier. Eulerian–lagrangian cfd-microphysics modeling of a near-field contrail from a realistic turbofan. *International Journal of Engine Research*, 23(4):661–677, 2022.
- [15] Sébastien Cantin, François Morency, and François Garnier. Modeling capabilities on the formation of contrails in a commercial cfd code. 2019.
- [16] Harjot Singh Saluja, Feijia Yin, Arvind Gangoli Rao, and Volker Grewe. Effect of engine design parameters on the climate impact of aircraft: A case study based on short-medium range mission. *Aerospace*, 10(12):1004, 2023.
- [17] Antoine Guitton, Charles Tinney, Peter Jordan, and Joel Delville. Measurements in a co-axial subsonic jet. In *45th AIAA aerospace sciences meeting and exhibit*, page 15, 2007.
- [18] James Bridges and Mark Wernet. Establishing consensus turbulence statistics for hot subsonic jets. In *16th AIAA/CEAS aeroacoustics conference*, page 3751, 2010.
- [19] Ulrike Lohmann, F Luond, and Fabian Mahrt. An introduction to clouds.
- [20] D. Sonntag. Advancements in the field of hygrometry. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, pages 51–66, May 1994. Publisher: Schweizerbart’sche Verlagsbuchhandlung.